

Glucose Solution as a Vehicle for ROS-Enhancing Ferrocene Drugs

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Abstract

Recent advances in the use of ferrocene-based drugs—stimulated by their efficient application in cancer treatment and enhancement of neutrophil functions—require an effective delivery system. Here, we compare the effects of repeated subcutaneous injections of a ROS-inducing aminoferrocene compound, N-ferrocenyl-N-[4-(1-piperidinylmethyl)benzyl]aminocarboxymethyl-phenylboronic acid pinacol ester, (referred to as NCure2 or ROS-AFC; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 56 (2017), 15545). Previously studied as a 100% DMSO solution, its use was limited in clinical settings. We now dissolved the compound in: a) water; b) Smoflipid 20 (a 20% lipid-in-water emulsion, with Intralipid 20 as an analog); and c) 5% glucose (Glc) solution, commonly used for intravenous injection. We assessed compound absorbance, accumulation at injection sites, and tissue compatibility. Solutions at 7.2 mg/mL (50 μ L, equating to 12 mg/kg) were injected subcutaneously to balb/c mice every other day for a total of five injections. Vehicle-only controls were included.

Upon inspection, we observed precipitation with water and 10% DMSO solutions, lipid-filled granulomatous accumulation in Smoflipid 20, and complete absorption with no visible tissue damage when 5% Glc was used. Injection of ROS-AFC in 5% Glc significantly enhanced neutrophil elastase activity at sites of inflammation in a murine gout model (*ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2025, 17, 6, 9140–9154). In conclusion, 5% glucose stabilizes ROS-AFC at the injection site and enables its efficient absorption, suggesting its suitability as a clinical vehicle for ROS-AFC.

Introduction

Ferrocene-based drugs has a strong potential in multiple pharmaceutical applications, perfectly reviewed in [1]. Aminoferrocenes have been shown to effectively elevate ROS levels through a NOX2-independent mechanism by auto-amplifying existing ROS species. These compounds successfully overwhelm the antioxidant defenses of cancer cells, inducing cytotoxicity via lysosomes [2], mitochondria [3], or endoplasmic reticulum [4], and enhance neutrophil function via ROS-dependent manner [5]. The high anticancer efficacy and the development of efficient synthetic methods [6] for the NCure2 for NCure2 have prompted efforts to identify more biocompatible delivery systems. The use of 100% DMSO poses toxicity concerns that hinder clinical translation [7]. Thus, we tested water, 10% DMSO, 20% lipid emulsion, and 5% glucose as delivery vehicles for repeated subcutaneous injections of ROS-AFC.

Results and discussion

ROS-AFC dissolved uniformly in all vehicles at 7,2 mg/ml, forming either a clear or homogeneously colored suspension (in the lipid vehicle). Injection was done according to the experimental scheme at Figure 1.

Figure 1. Experimental scheme.

Injection of DMSO or ROS-AFC in DMSO caused deep subcutaneous wounds and extensive bleeding upon dissection (Figure 2, orange squares). Use of 10% DMSO reduced tissue damage, but yellow precipitates of ROS-AFC were still visible at the injection site (red squares) indicating the existence of the limit of the potentially bioavailable compound.

Figure 2. Places of injection ROS-AFC injection based on DMSO solvent.

In contrast, injections of 5% glucose or ROS-AFC in 5% glucose caused no irritation, visible precipitates, or tissue damage (Figure 3, green squares). ROS-AFC in water led to visible subcutaneous precipitates (red squares), suggesting that glucose stabilizes the compound and promotes absorption, although the mechanism remains unclear.

Figure 3. Injection sites with ROS-AFC in 5% glucose and water.

Injections with Smoflipid 20, either alone or containing ROS-AFC, led to subcutaneous yellow lipid deposits (Figure 4, red squares), consistent with poor solubility and local tissue damage. While Smoflipid 20 is approved for clinical use in Ukraine, similar results are expected with comparable lipid-in-water emulsions like Intralipid 20.

Figure 4. Injection sites with ROS-AFC in Smoflipid 20.

Given these results, ROS-AFC in 5% glucose—referred to as NCure80—was selected for further testing. In a gout model, mice received MSU crystals in the left footpad (inducing inflammation) and saline in the right footpad. MSU microneedles are known to induce neutrophil recruitment and ROS-dependent neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) formation [8], eventually leading to sequestration of MSU crystals and resolution of inflammation [9]. NCure80 was injected intraperitoneally at 20 mg/kg to some mice being compared to those did not receiving the injection. Fluorescent imaging was done to monitor presence of externalized neutrophil elastase (probe SQ-215-NETP, fig 10) and extracellular neutrophil elastase activity (probe Hetero-APA, fig 7) [10]. Comparison of NCure80 treated and untreated mice revealed enhanced neutrophil elastase activity in inflamed sites, indicating increased NET formation [10]. Supplementary Figure 1 presents republished imaging data (under BY-NC-ND 4.0 license) demonstrating the action of ROS-AFC in 5% glucose solution on enhancing local NETs formation at the place of gout induction, is republished from original study in [10].

Experimental

Reagents

Smoflipid 20 (Fresenius Kabi Deutschland GmbH) contains 60 g soybean oil, 60 g medium-chain triglycerides, 50 g olive oil, and 30 g fish oil per liter and is approved for use in Ukraine as an intravenous solvent, analogous to Intralipid 20. 5% Glucose solution was obtained from Yuria-Pharm LLC (Ukraine); DMSO from Sigma-Aldrich.

ROS-AFC was synthesized by Prof. Mokhir's group within the NeutroCure.eu project. All solutions (7.2 mg/mL) were prepared fresh and used within 2 hours.

Animals Studies

Studies involving animals, including housing and care, method of euthanasia, and experimental protocols were approved by the Ethical Committee of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University, protocols 20200525/4, 20230831/8, all experiments were designed to comply with principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement). Mice were housed in a temperature/humidity/light controlled environment, with both food and drinking water available ad libitum.

Balb/c mice (12–14 weeks, ~30 g) were grouped (n=3) and injected with:

- DMSO
- ROS-AFC in DMSO
- ROS-AFC in 10% DMSO
- ROS-AFC in 5% Glucose
- 5% Glucose
- ROS-AFC in Smoflipid 20
- Smoflipid 20

Injections (50 μ L) were made subcutaneously with insulin syringe on the dorsal skin every second day, five times in non-overlapping sites (see Figure 1). Injection sites were monitored and photographed.

Conclusions

5% Glucose solution stabilizes ROS-enhancing aminoferrocene drugs, enabling their efficient absorption after repeated subcutaneous administration. It also enhances NET formation via ROS-dependent mechanisms *in vivo*. Glucose and similar clinically approved sugar-based vehicles (e.g., mannitol) represent promising delivery systems for aminoferrocene-based therapeutics, avoiding complications associated with DMSO and lipid emulsions.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used GPT-4-turbo in order to enhance text readability in introduction section. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Supporting Information Additional

A reprint of the figure demonstrating compound efficacy in the *in vivo* inflammation model is provided.

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Supplementary Figure S1. Places of injection ROS-AFC injection based on 5% glucose and water. IP injection of extracellular neutrophil-elastase probe SQ-215-NETP in MSU-induced gout inflammation: mice A: left paw (L) with MSU and the right paw (R) with saline; mice B: left paw with MSU & additional NCure80 to induce gout and right paw with saline.

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